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INTRAOPERATIVE BLOOD MANAGEMENT IN PEDIATRIC SCOLIOSIS SURGERY – OUR FIRST EXPERIENCE

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Introduction. Surgical correction of scoliosis is a major procedure with considerable risk of intraoperative bleeding.

Aim. The aim of this study was to analyse the resuscitation of fluids, blood and blood derivatives during corrective scoliosis surgeries in children.

Material and methods. The research was conducted as a clinical retrospective study that included patients who underwent corrective scoliosis surgery at the Pediatric Surgery Clinic in Novi Sad, from February 2020 to October 2022. The study included 31 patients aged 8 to 18 years. By examining medical documentation, the following were analyzed: basic patient data, diagnosis, comorbidities, ASA status. Data related to intraoperative fluid resuscitation were analyzed: total amount of fluids, total amount of crystalloids, use of autologous and heterologous transfusion, use of cell saver.

Results. During the operation, an average of 3344.97 ml of fluid was given per patient. For crystalloids, the average was 2454.16 ml. Colloids were administered in 22 patients, ranging from 3 to 30 ml/kg. 5% Albumin was given in a range of 2 to 6 ml/kg, with a mean value of 4.21 ml/kg in 7 patients. Fresh frozen plasma was given to 15 patients, from 4.5 to 20 ml/kg. 18 patients received blood transfusion, M=8.55 ml/kg. Autologous transfusion was received by 17 patients, from 1.5 ml/kg to 15 ml/kg. In premedication, 29 patients received tranexamic acid, the dose was 20 mg/kg, that was continued during surgery, at a dose of 2-5 mg/kg/h.

Discussion. Scoliosis surgery is often associated with substantial blood loss and potentially detrimental effects in patients, therefore, adequate preoperative preparation and timely recognition of patients with an increased risk of bleeding are important. Understanding of fluid resuscitation and blood management techniques improves surgical planning, limits transfusion related complications and optimizes outcomes in pediatric population.